

Speed in Lorentz Transformation Directly Linked to Increased Momentum Hence Impulse?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 20, 2025

The author of (1) argues that the fact that the speed of light is the same in all frames is linked to the human perception of space-time, but that what is important are interactions. In particular, (1) talks of electric and magnetic fields as being linked to acceleration.

Here, we try to make the same argument, but based directly on the Lorentz transformation. One may derive the Lorentz transformation strictly for a transformation of (x, ct) which suggests that it is about space-time, just as the Galilean transformation also seems to pertain strictly to space-time. Interestingly, however, (pc, E) transform according to the same Lorentz transformation. Furthermore, the laws of physics (interaction laws) are the same in each frame. Thus, we argue that a Lorentz transformation is really about interactions and not so much about space-time. In other words, the idea of a moving frame $(-v)$ means a rest mass m_0 at moving with v is not so much about space-time as it is about a change of momentum which may result in an impulse hit. Even a photon (which has a constant speed c) has its momentum changed when seen by a moving frame. Thus, the v of the transformation is really about changing the momentum and hence impulse, not the motion c . This, we argue, is why c may be the same in all frames and is not affected by a moving frame $(-v)$. The speed of the photon in a vacuum has nothing to do with its momentum and hence impulse, i.e. $E=pc$. The change in speed as seen in a moving frame pertains only to change in momentum and we argue that this is the key point. Thus, it is an interaction statement (ultimately). Speed itself requires spatial and time measurements and clocks and rulers are different in different frames, but an impulse which breaks a target does so in any frame.

One may see that by deriving the Lorentz transformation for x, t that one introduces a parameter b with speed units so that x , and bt have the same units. This b is the same in all frames and so is seemingly not affected by the $-v$ of the frame, but should nevertheless be a real speed. How can this be? If the same Lorentz transformation affects (pb, E) , then one may argue that b has nothing to do with an increasing E or p (interaction variables). In other words, $E=pb$ for any E, p pair (for a photon).

Finally, as (1) states, the key idea seems to be interaction and we argue that this idea follows directly from the Lorentz transformation. If b is not frame dependent, then it seems that it should follow from parameters in space and we try to argue that these parameters appear in the electromagnetic potential.

Physical Implications of a Moving Frame

A frame moving with constant speed $-v$ must have been accelerated and this involved work. For the moving frame to see an object with rest mass, m_0 , now move with v seems to imply that work was done on this rest mass m_0 . The idea of the v motion is directly linked with work and not so much with space time motion we argue. We suggest that the notion of a frame with $-v$ changes momentum and E in (pc, E) and so changes in impulse (whether a particle has a rest

mass or not) because the moving frame is in motion due to work done on it. One cannot escape the notion of the $-v$ frame being linked to force and work because (pc, E) transform according to the same Lorentz transformation which affects (x, ct) . As a result, the change of speed as seen in a moving frame is not really a description about motion unless this motion is linked with changed p , i.e. changed impulse. The moving frame does not simply change a speed (say c the speed of light), unless there are consequences on the momentum and impulse. In the case of light, $E=pc$, and so a change in E and p (and hence impulse) may occur with no change in c . Thus, c is not linked to a change as seen by a moving frame $-v$, we argue. Mathematically one may show that $x/t=c$ and $x'/t'=c$ hold for a Lorentz transformation for a photon and so one may see that the Lorentz transformation is not simply about changing a speed as seen from a frame moving with $-v$.

(Note: $x' = g(v) v t$ and $t' = g(v) t$ with $x/t = c$. Then:

$$x'/t' = c \text{ and } xx - cctt = x'x' - cc t't' \text{ implies that: } g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((1))$$

Galilean Transformation

The Galilean transformation states that a frame moves with velocity v_1 and a particle in the frame, with velocity v_2 , then as seen from the rest frame:

$$v \text{ of particle} = v_1 + v_2 \quad ((2))$$

This transformation seems to pertain strictly to motion, but we argue that the velocity v_1 involved means that the particle in the moving frame has more momentum relative to the rest frame and this may contribute to an impact. In fact, a rest mass in the moving frame has no momentum relative to that frame, but has momentum relative to the rest frame and will demonstrate this with a collision with a large rest object. Thus, momentum and impulse seem to be as key ideas as motion in the Galilean transformation.

Spacetime Derivation of the Lorentz Transformation

It is possible to derive the Lorentz transformation strictly from x, t considerations and a moving frame $(-v)$. This gives the sense that the transformation is focused entirely on motion, but we argue that this cannot be the case if the same transformation is to apply to (pc, E) . The Lorentz transformation is linked with a moving frame $(-v)$ and is guaranteed to change p (momentum) and hence impulse. Thus, the Lorentz transformation seems to be largely about impulse and interactions. One may argue that someone in the rest frame sees an object moving say faster towards them and that this is physical. This statement, however, is linked with space and time measurements and so the physicality is in the measurements. An impulse may create damage which has nothing to do with time or space measurements, i.e. it may break a target or dent it.

If one has an object with rest mass, m_0 , at rest at $x=0$, t , then as seen in a frame moving with $-v$, one has:

$$x'/t' = v \quad ((3))$$

This leads to: $x' = g(v/b) v t$ and $t' = g(v/b) t$ ((4)) $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb}$

Here b is a constant with units of speed, i.e. it is the same in all frames. How can this be? We argue that the motion the moving frame assigns to an object must also correspond to a change in momentum. In the rest frame, one has $E=mc^2$ and $p=0$ and this transforms like x, t in ((4)). If a speed has nothing to do with a momentum change, as in $E=pc$ for a photon, then the moving frame does not augment this speed, it seems. Thus, interaction is key as argued in (1).

For a photon, $x/t=c$ and $x'/t'=c$, but the transformation (Lorentz) used in ((4)) still applies and also applies to (pc, E) where $E=pc$.

Speed of Light and Parameters of Space

If the speed of light is not changed by a moving frame $-v$, i.e. not linked with a change in p (impulse), then one may suggest it is a constant because it is a function of parameters in space which do not change as seen from a moving frame. We suggest that such a parameter appears in the electrostatic potential energy:

$$\phi(r) = q/(4\pi\epsilon_0) 1/r \quad ((4)) \quad (\text{Point charge})$$

Q (charge) is a parameter like m_0 (rest mass), but ϵ_0 is a parameter describing space and it does not change in a Lorentz transformation. If one considers pc, E as transforming under a Lorentz transformation then, Q, q, ϕ should transform in the same manner because $q\phi$ is an energy. This means that:

$$\phi' = g(v) \phi \quad \text{and} \quad A' c = g(v) v/c \phi \quad ((5))$$

Now ϕ contains $1/\epsilon_0$ and so A' is proportional to: $1/c^2 (1/\epsilon_0)$ and ϕ' , to $1/\epsilon_0$. If one wishes ϕ' and A' to depend on parameters of space which are unchanged by a $-v$ frame transformation, then:

$$1/\epsilon_0 \text{ is linked with } \phi \quad \text{and} \quad c^2 = 1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0} \quad ((6))$$

so A is linked with $1/\mu_0$. This means that c , a speed (that of light) is actually expressed in terms of parameters of space which do not change as seen from different moving frames, i.e.

$$c = 1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0} \quad ((7))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, (1) presents the argument that the speed of light is not augmented by a person moving in a frame with speed $-v$. (1) suggests that this is due to the fact that interactions are key. We concur and try to argue this directly from the Lorentz transformation. The key idea is that not only (x, ct) , but also (pc, E) transform according to the same Lorentz transformation. This means that one is forced to have change in p (momentum) and hence impulse if the speed of a particle changes as seen in a moving frame. Thus, the Lorentz transformation is strongly focused on changes in E and p , even for a photon. One may argue that for a particle with rest mass, its speed (which is directly linked to momentum) changes and this seems to be physical, but it is only physical based on space and time measurements and clocks and rulers give different values in different moving frames. An impulse, however, that breaks a target, breaks it in all frames. We suggest that the impulse view of a Lorentz transformation is key and given $E=pc$, changes in E and p do not change c and so c , the speed of light in a vacuum, should not be augmented as seen by a moving frame. We then argue that this speed c should follow from properties of space which do not change when seen from a moving frame. We suggest that ϵ_0 , the electrical permittivity and a corresponding μ_0 (for the vector magnetic potential) satisfy this condition.

References

1. Segale, M. An Explanation as to why the Light velocity is the maximum attainable velocity value (Aug. 2024) https://osf.io/preprints/osf/5hfsp_v1